

SENSITIVITY AND UNCERTAINTY OF MODAL CHARACTERISTICS AND FORCED RESPONSE OF BLADED DISKS MISTUNED BY MATERIAL ANISOTROPY

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ABSTRACT

A method is developed for the calculation of the sensitivities of modal characteristics and forced response of material anisotropy mistuned bladed disk with respect to crystal orientation using high-fidelity finite element models. An efficient approach using gradient based polynomial chaos is developed to obtain statistical characteristics for forced response amplitudes with respect to variations in anisotropy orientations of blades in the bladed disk.

Numerical studies are carried out to analyze the effect of uncertainty in material anisotropy orientations on modal characteristics of tuned bladed disks and on forced response of mistuned bladed disks. The validation of the sensitivity calculation of the forced response with respect to anisotropy angles are carried out.

The sensitivities of the forced response are thoroughly analyzed for several excitation forces and mistuning patterns. The statistics for maximum forced response amplitudes are obtained using the polynomial chaos expansion and compared with the results calculated using Monte Carlo evaluations.

INTRODUCTION

The blades in the turbine stages in a gas turbine have to withstand high pressures and temperatures. In order to accommodate blades in this severe conditions, engineers have used blades consisting of directionally solidified and single crystal materials. Single crystal materials only consist of one columnar grain, therefore the grain boundaries can be avoided, which results in a material that has better creep resistance and extended fatigue life. During the casting process of the single crystal blades, the temperature is carefully controlled, which results in having the same orientation for all the crystals in the material. Because of this feature, the material behavior is anisotropic. Due to the difficulty of controlling the orientation of the crystals in the monocrystal

talline material during casting, there is a significant scatter in the orientation of material anisotropy axes. The variation of the crystal orientation from blade to blade introduces anisotropy mistuning in the bladed disk assembly.

There is limited studies carried out on the effect of anisotropy axis variation of the single crystal blades on the static and dynamic response. The influence on fatigue life of single crystal blades has been investigated in [1] and in [2] probabilistic methods have been applied to assess low cycle fatigue life. The dependency of static elastic stresses on the crystal orientation for tuned bladed disks were investigated by Savage [3]. The variation of natural frequencies due to crystal orientation scatter for turbine buckets have been analyzed in [4] by numerical and experimental means. Kaneko [5] used simple plate models to investigate the influence of anisotropy axis orientation on the natural frequencies of single crystal and directionally solidified materials. Kosco and Petrov [6] has developed a method for calculating sensitivity of the modal characteristics of high-fidelity models of anisotropy mistuned bladed disks. The mistuning effect due to anisotropy scatter on forced response has been analyzed in [7] using the fundamental reduction model (see Ref. [8]). Zang and Petrov [9] has developed a method with high-fidelity reduction approach for the calculation of the forced response analysis for anisotropy mistuned bladed disks.

Uncertainty analysis (UA) often requires numerous evaluations of computational models based on the sampling of input parameter space. The computational cost of UA using conventional Monte Carlo methods are prohibitive when using high-fidelity FE models. Therefore, in order to perform UA, the use of computationally inexpensive surrogate models that can closely approximate the FE model is very attractive.

The surrogate models based on polynomial chaos ex-

pansion (PCE) have been studied extensively for its usefulness in quantifying uncertainty in dynamic systems [10, 11]. The main feature of PCE is the decomposition of output response into a linear combination of deterministic and stochastic components. The computational effort in obtaining PCE is associated with calculation of coefficients in the expansion based on finite number of realizations of deterministic FE model of the bladed disks. Panunzio et al. [12] used PCE to study the effects of uncertainty in tip-casing gap on nonlinear normal modes of turbine blades. Considering the modal stiffness of blades as random variables, Sinha [13] obtained the statistics of forced response for mistuned bladed disks using PCE. Rahul and Petrov [14] used gradient enhanced polynomial chaos expansion to obtain the statistical characteristics of scatter in static displacements due to random anisotropy orientation of blades in bladed disks with material anisotropy mistuning.

In this paper the analysis of the influence of the crystal orientation scatter on modal and dynamic properties is carried out for a high-fidelity anisotropy mistuned blade disk model. The sensitivities of the forced response of the mistuned bladed disk with respect to the anisotropy angles are calculated and analyzed for several excitation forces and mistuning patterns.

In order to quantify the effect of uncertainty in anisotropy orientation, the statistical characteristics for modal properties and forced response are obtained. Gradient based PCE is presented as an efficient alternative to computationally intensive Monte Carlo method. The statistics for maximum forced response amplitude obtained using gradient based PCE is compared with those obtained using Monte Carlo evaluations.

MATERIAL ANISOTROPY MISTUNING MODELING

For a linear-elastic material the stress-strain relation can be written as

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon} \quad (1)$$

where, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ are the stress and strain tensors respectively in Voigt notation and \mathbf{C} is the elasticity tensor. Anisotropic materials have different material properties in different directions, which for the most general case results in 21 independent parameters in the elasticity tensor \mathbf{C} . The modern blades used in turbine stages are consisting of nickel-base superalloy single crystal materials. These materials are orthotropic and because in the crystal structure an additional symmetry is introduced, there are only 3 independent parameters in the elasticity tensor \mathbf{C} .

In order to be able to calculate with finite element matrices, the stress-strain relation Eq. (1) has to be transformed into the global coordinate system (CS). The transformation of the elasticity tensor for linear-elastic materials can be executed from the CS attached to every blade to the global CS with the help of the stress transformation matrix \mathbf{T} as:

$$\mathbf{C}^*(\mathbf{R}_M, \mathbf{R}_B) = \mathbf{T}(\mathbf{R}_M, \mathbf{R}_B) \mathbf{C} \mathbf{T}^T(\mathbf{R}_M, \mathbf{R}_B) \quad (2)$$

The stress transformation matrix \mathbf{T} is dependent on the rotation matrices \mathbf{R}_M and \mathbf{R}_B . The rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_B defines the position of the stacking axis in the global CS and

Fig. 1: Definition of the material and blade coordinate system

\mathbf{R}_M defines the orientation of the blade material in the coordinate system of the blades.

The anisotropy angles α, β and ζ , that the rotation matrix \mathbf{R}_M is dependent on, are measured by the blade manufacturer after casting. The primary angle α defines the deviation of [001] material axis from the blade stacking axis z' , the secondary angle β is determined as the angle between [100] axis and the x' axis moreover, the angle ζ defines the position of the axis [001] axis on a polar coordinate basis. For the anisotropy angles statistical distribution is provided by the blade manufacturer, which has been used in the current work, but is not provided here due to confidentiality restrictions.

The element stiffness matrix can be calculated using the element stiffness formulation for 3D isoparametric elements:

$$\mathbf{k}^e = \int_{V^e} \mathbf{B}^T \mathbf{C}^* \mathbf{B} dV \quad (3)$$

Where \mathbf{k}^e is the finite element stiffness matrix, \mathbf{C}^* is the elasticity matrix defined in the global coordinate system, \mathbf{B} is the strain-displacement matrix and V^e is the volume of the element. The global stiffness matrix \mathbf{K} can be assembled by adding the expanded element stiffness matrices together, after which the finite element calculations for the whole structure can be carried out.

METHOD FOR ANALYSIS OF SENSITIVITY TO ANISOTROPY MISTUNING

In this section the sensitivities of the natural frequencies, modes shapes and forced response are derived with respect to material anisotropy angles: $\gamma = \alpha, \beta, \zeta$ for any b^{th} blade in a bladed disk ($b \in [1 \dots N]$).

Sensitivity of Modal Characteristics of Multi-Degree-of-Freedom Systems

The derivatives of eigenvalues and mode shapes of a multi-degree-of-freedom (MDOF) system with respect to the anisotropy angles has to be calculated in order to as-

sess the sensitivities of the modal properties. The eigenvalue problem of the MDOF dynamic systems is formed for the whole anisotropy-mistuned bladed disk in the form:

$$\mathbf{K}\boldsymbol{\phi}_j = \lambda_j \mathbf{M}\boldsymbol{\phi}_j \quad (4)$$

where the stiffness matrix denoted as \mathbf{K} , the eigenvalue λ_j and the mode shape $\boldsymbol{\phi}_j$, are dependent on the anisotropy axis orientation, but the mass matrix \mathbf{M} is not moreover, subscript j denotes the mode number. By taking the derivative of Eq. (4) with respect to γ and considering mass normalized mode shapes, the sensitivity of the eigenvalues for a MDOF dynamic system results in [15]:

$$\frac{\partial \lambda_j}{\partial \gamma} = \boldsymbol{\phi}_j^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \gamma} \boldsymbol{\phi}_j \quad (5)$$

where γ can be any anisotropy angle defining the crystal orientation of the blade material. The derivative of the stiffness matrix in Eq. (5) is calculated by the numerical scheme of finite differences described in detail in [6].

The calculation of the sensitivity of mode shapes with respect to the anisotropy parameters is carried out using an enhanced method presented in [6]. The derivative of the eigenvectors are expressed by a series expansion formulation that accounts for the terms that are not included in the expansion:

$$\frac{\partial \boldsymbol{\phi}_j}{\partial \gamma} = \sum_{k=1}^m c_{jk} \boldsymbol{\phi}_k + \mathbf{r}_j \quad (6)$$

The coefficients of the series expansion in Eq. (6) can be expressed as:

$$c_{jk} = \begin{cases} \frac{\lambda_j - \lambda_0}{(\lambda_k - \lambda_j)(\lambda_k - \lambda_0)} \boldsymbol{\phi}_k^T \mathbf{f}_j & \text{if } k \neq j \\ -\frac{\boldsymbol{\phi}_k^T \mathbf{f}_j}{\lambda_k - \lambda_0} & \text{if } k = j \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The residual term in Eq. (6) can be calculated by solving the system of linear equation:

$$(\mathbf{K} - \lambda_0 \mathbf{M}) \mathbf{r}_j = \mathbf{f}_j \quad (8)$$

The term \mathbf{f}_j introduced in Eq. (7) and (8) can be calculated as:

$$\mathbf{f}_j = -\left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \gamma} - \frac{\partial \lambda_j}{\partial \gamma} \mathbf{M} \right) \boldsymbol{\phi}_j \quad (9)$$

The reference frequency λ_0 is chosen for each mode shape as:

$$\lambda_0 = \frac{\lambda_j + \lambda_{j-1}}{2} \quad (10)$$

The derivative of the stiffness matrix in Eq. (5) is calculated element-wise in the open-source finite element program CalculiX [6, 16] by using the stiffness element formulation:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{k}^e}{\partial \gamma} = \int_{V^e} \mathbf{B}^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{C}^*}{\partial \gamma} \mathbf{B} dV \quad (11)$$

where $\partial \mathbf{C}^*/\partial \gamma$, the derivative of the elasticity matrix with respect to an anisotropy angle is defined as:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{C}^*}{\partial \gamma} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{T}}{\partial \gamma} \mathbf{C} \mathbf{T}^T + \mathbf{T} \mathbf{C} \frac{\partial \mathbf{T}^T}{\partial \gamma} \quad (12)$$

The right hand side term in Eq. (5) is calculated on the element level and then standard stiffness matrix assembly procedure is used, leading to:

$$\boldsymbol{\phi}_j^T \frac{\partial \mathbf{K}}{\partial \gamma} \boldsymbol{\phi}_j = \boldsymbol{\phi}_j^T \left(\bigcup_e \frac{\partial \mathbf{k}^e}{\partial \gamma} \boldsymbol{\phi}_j^e \right) \quad (13)$$

Forced Response and its Sensitivity Calculations

The equation of motion for a mistuned structure for a case of harmonic excitation $\mathbf{f}(t) = \mathbf{F} e^{i\omega t}$ when the forced response is also harmonic $\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{X} e^{i\omega t}$ takes the form:

$$[\mathbf{K} + i\mathbf{D} - \omega^2 \mathbf{M}] \mathbf{X} = \mathbf{F} \quad (14)$$

For the engine order excitation by k -th excitation harmonic, the phase shift between neighboring sectors of a bladed disk is equal to $e^{i\alpha k}$, where $\alpha = 2\pi/N$ and N is the total number of blades in the bladed disk, and the force vector for the whole structure takes the following form:

$$\mathbf{F} = \left\{ \mathbf{F}^S, e^{i\alpha k} \mathbf{F}^S, \dots, e^{i\alpha k(N_B-1)} \mathbf{F}^S \right\}^T \quad (15)$$

where \mathbf{F}^S is the distribution of the complex amplitude of excitation load over one sector of a bladed disk. Using the mode shapes and natural frequencies calculated for the high-fidelity model of an anisotropy-mistuned bladed disk, the amplitudes, \mathbf{X} , are calculated through modal characteristics of the mistuned bladed disk as:

$$\mathbf{X} = \sum_{j=1}^n \frac{\boldsymbol{\phi}_j^T \mathbf{F}}{(1 + i\eta_j)\omega_j^2 - \omega^2} \boldsymbol{\phi}_j = \sum_{j=1}^n c_j \boldsymbol{\phi}_j \quad (16)$$

where n is the number of mode shapes kept in the analysis, η_j is the modal damping factor for j -th mode, ω_j is the eigenvalue and $\boldsymbol{\phi}_j$ is the corresponding mode shape of a mistuned structure. It should be noted that the blade amplitudes can be calculated using this formula for any set of nodes selected from the whole structure, which reduces significantly the computational time by selecting a set of nodes of interest from the whole finite element of a bladed disk. This set of nodes contains usually several hundred or thousand DOFs while the whole FE model can contain millions DOFs. The sensitivity of the forced response with respect to the angles characterising orientation of the material anisotropy with respect to blade stacking angles is obtained by differentiating Eq. 16 with respect to the anisotropy angle of interest:

$$\mathbf{X}' = \sum_{j=1}^n c'_j \boldsymbol{\phi}_j + c_j \boldsymbol{\phi}'_j \quad (17)$$

where the prime symbol indicate the derivative, $\partial/\partial \gamma$ and the derivative of the modal expansion coefficient is expressed in the following form:

$$c'_j = \frac{\mathbf{F}^T \boldsymbol{\phi}'_j}{(1 + i\eta_j)\omega_j^2 - \omega^2} - \frac{\mathbf{F}^T \boldsymbol{\phi}_j \left[(1 + i\eta'_j)\omega_j^2 + 2(1 + i\eta_j)\omega_j \omega'_j \right]}{\left[(1 + i\eta_j)\omega_j^2 - \omega^2 \right]^2} \quad (18)$$

UNCERTAINTY ANALYSIS OF BLADED DISKS USING GRADIENT BASED POLYNOMIAL CHAOS EXPANSION

For a realistic high-fidelity models of bladed disk, the use of conventional Monte-Carlo based approach for uncertainty analysis could be prohibitive due to high computational cost, and therefore, the use of surrogate models are necessary. The idea behind PCE is to project the stochastic

output $y(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ in the n -dimensional random space spanned by orthogonal polynomial basis $\psi_i(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ which are functions of the n -dimensional random variable $\boldsymbol{\xi} = \{\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_n\}$. For the considered case of bladed disk with random anisotropy angles, $\boldsymbol{\xi}$, the output function, which can be displacement, stress or modal characteristics like natural frequency, could be expanded using PCE as shown in Eq.(19)

$$y(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} c_i \psi_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \approx \sum_{i=0}^P c_i \psi_i(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \quad (19)$$

where, c_i are unknown coefficients in the expansion that need to be evaluated. For practical reasons, the series could be truncated by limiting the order of basis polynomials, p . The orthogonality of the basis functions w.r.t. the probability distribution of the random variables implies that the inner product of the function satisfy Eq.(20)

$$\langle \psi_r(\boldsymbol{\xi}), \psi_s(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \rangle = \int_{\Omega} \psi_r(\boldsymbol{\xi}) \psi_s(\boldsymbol{\xi}) d\mu(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \gamma_n \delta_{rs} \quad (20)$$

where, γ_n are constants, δ_{rs} is the Kronecker delta and $d\mu(\boldsymbol{\xi})$ is the probability measure in the n -dimensional random space given by Eq.(21) for statistically independent random variables

$$d\mu(\boldsymbol{\xi}) = \rho_1(\xi_1) \rho_2(\xi_2) \dots \rho_n(\xi_n) d\xi_1 d\xi_2 \dots d\xi_n \quad (21)$$

where, ρ_n is the probability density function of ξ_n . The choice of basis functions in Eq.(19) is based on the probability distribution of the random variables. Table 1 provides examples of basis functions for some common random distributions: (i) normal distribution, (ii) uniform distribution and (iii) exponential distribution: $\rho = \lambda e^{-\lambda \xi}$. For conciseness, the basis functions are provided here for special values of the parameters of the statistical distributions: (i) mean value, $\mu = 0$ and standard deviation (STD), $\sigma = 1$ - for normal distribution; (ii) uniform distribution is taken over interval $[-1, 1]$; $\lambda = 1$ is assumed for exponential distribution. The basis function expressions can be generalized and obtained for any realistic parameter values of these and many other distributions. For the case of multivariate output function, the polynomial basis functions are obtained as tensor products of orthogonal polynomial basis for corresponding univariate cases.

TABLE 1: Choice of basis functions

Distribution	Polynomial	Basis terms
Normal ($\mu = 0, \sigma = 1$)	Hermite	$\psi_0 = 1, \psi_1 = \xi,$ $\psi_2 = (\xi^2 - 1)/\sqrt{2}, \dots$
Uniform ($-1, 1$)	Legendre	$\psi_0 = 1, \psi_1 = \sqrt{3}\xi,$ $\psi_2 = \sqrt{5}(3\xi^2 - 1)/2, \dots$
Exponential ($\lambda = 1$)	Laguerre	$\psi_0 = 1, \psi_1 = \xi - 1,$ $\psi_2 = (\xi^2 - 4\xi + 2)/2, \dots$

When the number of realizations of the exact model is greater than the number of coefficients in Eq.(19), then the system of linear equations is overdetermined and is solved using the least squares approach.

Polynomial chaos expansion using gradient information.

The number of terms in PCE increases exponentially as the dimension of random space increases, increasing the computational cost. This problem is often referred in the literature as the ‘‘curse of dimensionality’’. To address this problem, the use of gradient values in evaluating the coefficients of polynomial response surfaces for maximum amplitude of vibrations in mistuned bladed disks was proved to be very useful (see Refs. [17], [18]) For an n -dimensional random space, the number of linearly independent equations obtained by including gradient values is $(1 + n)$ times the number of FE realizations where n is the number of random variables. Therefore, the minimum number of model realizations required to obtain the coefficients in a polynomial approximation is reduced by a factor of $1/(1 + n)$. The gradient of stochastic w.r.t. random design parameters evaluated at chosen points are used to determine the coefficients of PCE:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \psi_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1) & \psi_1(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1) & \dots & \psi_P(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1) \\ \frac{\partial \psi_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1)}{\partial \xi_1} & \frac{\partial \psi_1(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1)}{\partial \xi_1} & \dots & \frac{\partial \psi_P(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1)}{\partial \xi_1} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \psi_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1)}{\partial \xi_n} & \frac{\partial \psi_1(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1)}{\partial \xi_n} & \dots & \frac{\partial \psi_P(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1)}{\partial \xi_n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \psi_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}_N) & \psi_1(\boldsymbol{\xi}_N) & \dots & \psi_P(\boldsymbol{\xi}_N) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \frac{\partial \psi_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}_N)}{\partial \xi_n} & \frac{\partial \psi_1(\boldsymbol{\xi}_N)}{\partial \xi_n} & \dots & \frac{\partial \psi_P(\boldsymbol{\xi}_N)}{\partial \xi_n} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} c_0 \\ c_1 \\ \vdots \\ c_P \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} y(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1) \\ \frac{\partial y(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1)}{\partial \xi_1} \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial y(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1)}{\partial \xi_n} \\ \vdots \\ y(\boldsymbol{\xi}_N) \\ \vdots \\ \frac{\partial y(\boldsymbol{\xi}_N)}{\partial \xi_n} \end{bmatrix} \quad (22)$$

where, $\psi_0(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1), \psi_1(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1), \dots, \psi_P(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1)$ are basis functions evaluated at first sample point, c_0, c_1, \dots, c_P are deterministic coefficients in the polynomial expansion, and $y(\boldsymbol{\xi}_1), \dots, y(\boldsymbol{\xi}_N)$ are exact values of the output obtained from N number of FE model evaluations. $\partial y(\boldsymbol{\xi}_i)/\partial \xi_j$ represents the gradient value of output w.r.t. j^{th} random parameter evaluated for i^{th} model evaluation.

For a multivariate output function, the polynomial basis are obtained as tensor products of orthogonal polynomials for corresponding univariate case. The dimension of the tensor product increases exponentially with increase in number of random parameters, and therefore, increases the number of model realizations required. In this study, a cross truncation feature available in Chaospy [19], a Python tool box for uncertainty quantification, is used to truncate the full tensor product set, a-priori, by ignoring some of the higher order interactions of variables in the orthogonal basis set.

NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this work the analysis is carried out for a full finite element model of a realistic bladed disk shown in Fig. 2. The model consists of 75 blades. The contact interfaces between the shrouds and between the disk and blades are assumed to be stuck. The finite element model of the bladed disk has approximately 0.5 million nodes. The model is constrained

Fig. 2: Quarter of the bladed disk finite element model

at the end of the rim of the disk in axial direction and a centrifugal load of $8625rpm$ is applied in the static analysis. The static analysis is carried out with nonlinear geometric effects included. The node of interest for every blade has been selected at a node on the trailing edge of the blade, visible in Fig. 2.

For the numerical analyses the excitation forces with engine order 2, 7, 8, 11 and 35 have been chosen. This selection allows for the analysis of both disk and blade dominated modes. The engine order excitations and frequency ranges are indicated as A-K in Fig. 3.

The frequency values in this work are normalized with respect to the first natural frequency value of the stand-alone single sector of bladed disk. The finite element model has been fixed at the two symmetry planes of the disk and the same centrifugal loading is applied as for the bladed disk model.

Effect of Material Anisotropy Orientation on Modal Characteristics

To investigate the effects of uncertainty in material anisotropy orientation on modal characteristics, 150 different anisotropy orientations of a tuned bladed disk are analyzed. Different orientations are obtained by sampling from the known distribution of the anisotropy angles α , β and ζ (see Fig. 1a). For the first 12 mode families, the variation in mean and STD of frequencies as a function of EO is shown in Fig. 3. The mean values are plotted by lines and the STDs corresponding to each EO value are shown by bars for each EO value. In general, the influence of anisotropy orientation on frequency of vibration of bladed disk is significant for higher modes. For the modes studied, the variation in anisotropy angles can result in coefficient of variation of frequencies up to 2.1%.

Validation of the Sensitivity of Forced Response with Respect to Anisotropy Angles

The validation of the sensitivity of the forced response is presented here for the case of mistuned bladed disk. The mistuning is introduced by randomly generated anisotropy angles corresponding to their statistical distribution provided by the blade manufacturer. For the calculation of an

Fig. 3: Variation in mean value of the frequency of tuned bladed disk along with corresponding standard deviation w.r.t. EO excitation

Fig. 4: Normalized forced response of all 75 blades at 11EO for mode family 2

approximate of the forced response sensitivity, the finite difference method is used. First, the forced response is calculated with the randomly generated mistuning pattern. Second, the three anisotropy angles of one of the blades are increased by a small value one by one. Using the finite difference formula the sensitivity of the maximum nodal displacement with respect to any anisotropy angle of b^h blade can be calculated:

$$\frac{\partial a}{\partial \gamma_b} = \frac{a(\gamma_b + \Delta\gamma_b) - a(\gamma_b)}{\Delta\gamma_b} \quad (23)$$

where $\Delta\gamma_b = 0.001$ rad.

The 2nd mode family is excited of the bladed disk with engine order 11 excitation force, indicated as (H) in Fig. 3. The nodal displacements are normalized with the maximum forced response value of the tuned bladed disk, in which all anisotropy angles are $\alpha = \beta = \zeta = 0$. In Fig. 4 the normalized nodal forced response is shown for all 75 blades.

The capabilities of the newly implemented methods allow for the recovery of the displacements in the time domain at any excitation frequency. As an example the recovered displacements for all the nodes of the bladed disk are shown in Fig. 5 at the time-step when the largest displacements occur.

In order to carry out the validation of the forced response, the both forced response and sensitivity values have

Fig. 5: Recovered forced response in time domain of all 75 blades at 11EO for mode family 2 at $f = 4.608$

Fig. 6: Validation of sensitivities of the forced response with respect to α angle of blade 10 at $f = 4.608$

Fig. 7: Envelopes of the forced response calculated for 10 different anisotropy mistuning patterns at 8EO for mode family 1

to be calculated at the same excitation frequency. In Fig. 6 the sensitivities of the displacements of all blades with respect to the anisotropy angle α of blade number 10 can be seen at the normalized frequency $f = 4.608$. The sensitivities calculated with the new method and with finite differences are in good agreement. The small deviations visible in the figure are due to inferior precision in the sensitivity values calculated with finite difference method.

Fig. 8: Harmonic spectrum of the response for 8EO excitation of mode family 1 and 2

Effect of Anisotropy Scatter on the Forced Response of Mistuned Bladed Disks

The influence of the anisotropy scatter is visualized with the envelopes of the maximum normalized forced response for 2 tuned and for 10 mistuned bladed disks in Fig. 7. The 10 mistuning patterns are created using random anisotropy angles. The forced response is normalized with the maximum forced response value of the tuned blade when the material CS coincides the local CS of the blade, therefore $\alpha = \beta = \zeta = 0$, the other tuned response is calculated with a model, when all anisotropy angles have the mean value derived from the statistical distribution. The excitation force is engine order 8 and the 1st family of modes is being excited, (C). One can see that the resonance frequency of the mistuned bladed disks are between the resonance frequencies of the two tuned variants. The maximum amplification factor of 1.1 can be observed. Moreover, it is worth noting that the amplification factor of the tuned bladed with mean angles is lower than the tuned bladed disk with 0 anisotropy angles. For this resonance frequency the disk modes are more dominant, therefore the effect of the mistuning introduced in the blade material anisotropy is not significant however, the mistuning patterns can split these disk modes, which results in two separate resonances. The forced response calculated for the latter type of mistuning patterns can have higher amplification factor, e.g. pattern 3 and 6 in Fig. 7. The mode shapes of the anisotropy mistuned bladed disks do not significantly change for the disk dominated modes [6], therefore it can be assumed that the displacements of the forced response will have the same dominant nodal diameter as the engine order of the excitation. This can be proven by calculating the harmonic coefficients of the displacements in tangential direction using the fast Fourier transformation. This has been carried out for the response of the mistuning pattern 1 at the normalized resonance frequency of $f = 2.374$. The harmonic coefficients shown in Fig. 8 show that the response is dominantly made up from nodal diameter 8 mode and other nodal diameters are less significant in the response.

The envelopes of the forced response for the same 10 mistuning patterns and the two tuned variants are shown in Fig. 9 when the 2nd family of modes are excited with 8EO excitation force, (D). The resonance frequency of the bladed disks with mistuning pattern are higher than the

Fig. 9: Envelopes of the forced response calculated for 10 different anisotropy mistuning patterns at 8EO for mode family 2

tuned bladed disks. The maximum amplification factor value depending on the mistuning pattern can reach up to 2.7 and in the response there is many resonance peaks, which is due to blade dominated modes from the 1st family of modes that are also in this frequency range. By calculating the Fourier coefficients for the response of pattern 7 at its normalized resonance frequency of $f = 4.317$ an assessment can be made about the dominant modes in the forced response. Fig. 8 shows that the one of the dominant nodal diameter is nodal diameter 8 however, higher nodal diameter modes from the first family of modes are also excited.

The forced response of the 10 different mistuning patterns that were used earlier were calculated with the excitations indicated as A-K in Fig. 3. The mean maximum response is shown for these 10 mistuning patterns in Fig. 10.

The veering regions between mode family 5 and 6 have been analyzed for 7EO and 8EO excitations, (B) and (G) respectively. The mean amplification factor over the frequency range that covers the resonance of both of the modes are 2.69 and 1.61 for 7EO and 8EO respectively.

With the excitation order of 8 for the 4th family of modes (F), the fourth family of disk dominated modes and the second family of blade dominated modes are excited, which results in a higher mean amplification factor of 1.88.

The response of the 10 different mistuning patterns were analyzed for 35EO as well for the 1st, 2nd and 3rd mode families, (I), (J) and (K). The simulations showed maximum mean amplification factors for all the mistuning patterns 1.51, 1.33 and 1.31 for the 1st, 2nd and 3rd mode families respectively.

Sensitivity Analysis of Forced Response of Anisotropy Mistuned Bladed Disks

In Fig. 11 the normalized forced response of the anisotropy mistuned bladed disk with pattern 1 is shown for 8EO excitation of the first mode family (C), where the modes are disk dominated. The maximum forced response of every blade over the given frequency range is depicted in Fig. 12. In this figure, it can be seen that there is no blade that has significantly higher displacements than the others and an imperfect periodicity can be observed. The highest value of forced response is for blade number 21 at the nor-

Fig. 10: Mean amplification factors calculated for different EOs and frequency ranges

Fig. 11: Forced response of all the blades for 8EO excitation of mode family 1

malized frequency $f = 2.374$, therefore the sensitivities of the normalized maximum nodal displacement of blade 21 is shown with respect to the α angles of all the blades in Fig. 13. In this figure the frequency of the two resonance peaks of the response is shown with vertical lines. It can clearly be seen that all blades show a very similar behavior: the sensitivities w.r.t. all the blades are zero at the frequency where the blade 21 resonates moreover, the sensitivities are central symmetric to crossing of the 0 axis and the normalized resonance frequency of $f = 2.374$ in its vicinity. Because the sensitivities have opposite signs on the two side of the resonance frequency and because the sensitivity of the response is zero at its resonance peak, the change in this mistuned pattern would shift the resonance frequencies without significant change in amplification factor. This effect can also be seen in Fig. 7, where only small amplification factors are observed but with noteworthy frequency shifts. The values of the sensitivities with respect to α anisotropy angle of all blades at $f = 2.377$, where the maximum value of sensitivity is observed is show in Fig. 14. It is worth noting, for the modes that are not significantly distorted by the anisotropy mistuning pattern, sensitivities are small and have an imperfect periodic pattern.

The sensitivities of the bladed disk have been analyzed for the engine order 8 excitation that excites the 2nd family of modes (D), and as discussed earlier the blade dominated modes of the 1st family. The normalized forced response of the blades where the maximum amplification factor is 1.5 or above is visualized in Fig. 15 for the mistuning pattern 7. From the response, it is evident that localization occurs as only 11 blades from 75 have large amplification factors

Fig. 12: Maximum forced response for each blade for 8EO excitation of mode family 1 over $f \in [2.36, 2.41]$

Fig. 13: Sensitivity of the amplification factor at blade 21 with respect to the α angle of all the blades for 8EO excitation of mode family 1

Fig. 14: Sensitivity of the amplification factor at blade 21 with respect to the all anisotropy angles of all the blades for 8EO excitation at $f = 2.377$ of mode family 1

on this frequency range. The highest amplitude can be observed for blade 57 at $f = 4.316$ with the amplification factor of 2.47, for which the sensitivities with respect to all anisotropy angles for every blade is shown in Fig. 16. The sensitivities with respect to β and ζ are negligible compared to the primary α angles of a few blades. Moreover, the sensitivities for excitation (D) are significantly higher than sensitivities for excitation force (C), see Fig. 14. The forced response at the resonance frequency is the most sensitive to the blades that have high vibration amplitudes or is located in the vicinity of a blade that has high displacements. The neighboring blades can have a high influence on the forced response, as the coupling is high between the blades, because of the stuck shrouds. The sensitivities with respect

Fig. 15: Forced response of selected blades for 8EO excitation of mode family 2

Fig. 16: Sensitivity of the amplification factor at blade 57 with respect to the all anisotropy angles of all the blades for 8EO excitation at $f = 4.316$ of mode family 2

Fig. 17: Sensitivity of the amplification factor at blade 57 with respect to the α angle of selected blades for 8EO excitation of mode family 2

to selected α primary angles, that have great influence on the response, are shown over the frequency range around the resonance (denoted with a vertical line) in Fig. 17. For this case, the sensitivities at the resonance peak are not zero however, the minimum and maximum values of the sensitivities are in the vicinity of the resonance peak.

The sensitivity of the response for 35EO excitation has been analyzed for the 1st family of modes (I) with pattern 2, which provided the highest amplification factor of 1.85. In the response of all the blades that have an amplification factor higher than 1, shown in Fig. 18, it is clearly visible that anisotropy mistuning can introduce strong localization in the forced response for blade dominated modes. The maximum displacement is at blade 17, therefore the sensitivities of the forced response at this blade is under invest-

Fig. 18: Forced response of selected blades for 35EO excitation of mode family 1

Fig. 19: Sensitivity of the amplification factor at blade 17 with respect to the α angle of selected blades for 35EO excitation of mode family 1

tigation. The sensitivities of the forced response that are shown in Fig. 19 with respect to the α anisotropy angle of the blades that have the highest sensitivity over the frequency range near the resonance. In this figure, it can be seen that the blade where the maximum displacement occurs and its neighbors will have the highest sensitivity immediately before and after the resonance, but at the resonance it takes a very small value. This is a similar behavior that could be seen for the sensitivities of the disk dominated modes, with the difference that it is only valid with respect to the anisotropy angles of the blades that are in the vicinity of the localization.

Uncertainty Analysis of the Effects of Anisotropy Orientation on Forced Response of Mistuned Bladed Disks

To investigate the effects of scatter in anisotropy angles on forced response of a mistuned bladed disc, material anisotropy angles are randomly generated for all blades using realistic statistical distributions for each of the three blade material anisotropy angles. For statistical analysis, the three schemes of blades chosen for random variation of the anisotropy angles are used: (i) anisotropy angles of 30 blades are considered as random as shown in Fig.20(a), (ii) anisotropy angles of 37 blades are considered random as shown in Fig.20(b) and (iii) anisotropy angles of all 75 blades are considered random (Fig.20c).

For the case(i), 140 different mistuning patterns of bladed disk were obtained by sampling of anisotropy angles,

Fig. 20: Mistuned bladed disk with (a) 30 blades having random anisotropy angles, (b) 37 blades having random anisotropy angles, and (c) all 75 blades having random anisotropy angles.

from the known probability distribution of those angles, for the selected 30 blades (Fig. 20a) in the bladed disk. For different mistuning patterns analyzed, the scatter in maximum blade amplitude corresponding to excitation of first bending mode due to 8EO and 35EO is plotted in Fig. 21 (a) and (b) respectively. For the first bending mode, 8EO and 35EO excites a disk dominant mode and a blade dominant mode respectively (see Fig. 3). Therefore, intuitively the scatter in blade anisotropy angles must have larger influence on forced response due to 35EO excitation compared to that due to 8EO. This is evident from the comparison of the range of scatter in maximum blade amplitudes shown in Fig. 21(a) and (b). It can be seen in Fig. 21(b) that for 35EO excitation, while the maximum amplitude of all the selected 30 blades shows significant scatter, the maximum amplitude of some of the blades shows hardly any variation. As evident from Fig. 21(a), such drastic variation in scatter in maximum blade amplitude is not present in case of 8EO excitation, i.e. when the disk dominant mode is excited.

For the three different cases of bladed disks analysed, statistics of maximum blade response for mode 1 and mode 2 corresponding to 8EO and 35EO are shown in Fig. 22 and 23 respectively. From Fig. 22(a) it is evident that when a blade dominated mode is excited, the STD of normalized maximum response of the 30 blades whose anisotropy angles are varied is higher compared to that of blades with constant anisotropy angles. From comparison of Figs. 22(a), (b) and (c), it can be concluded that the mean and STD of maximum blade response corresponding to disk dominated modes do not vary significantly by increasing the number of random blade anisotropy angles accounted. From Fig. 23(a), (b) and (c) it can be inferred that in general, the STD of maximum blade response for 35EO excitation is higher for mode 1 compared to that for mode 2.

For case(ii) when anisotropy angles of all 75 blades are considered as random parameters, based on analysis of 900 different anisotropy mistuning patterns, uncertainty in forced response of bladed disk is investigated. Figs. 24 and 25 shows the histogram for normalized maximum response (known as amplification factor) for mode 1 and mode 2 respectively for 8EO and 35EO. The normalization is based on the maximum response of a tuned bladed disk with blade anisotropy angles aligned with the respective blade stacking axis. It is clear from Fig. 24(a) that for most of the mistun-

Fig. 21: Scatter in maximum blade response of bladed disk with 30 random blades for mode-1 under (a) 8EO and (b) 35EO.

ing patterns analysed the maximum response corresponding to 8EO excitation is only marginally higher than that of the tuned bladed disk when first bending mode is considered. As explained before, this is intuitive while considering that for mode 1, 8EO excites a disk dominant mode. For mode 2, both 8EO and 35EO excites blade dominant modes (see Fig. 3), and therefore, in contrast to that for mode 1, the mean amplification factor is higher for 8EO compared to that for 35EO excitation.

Uncertainty Analysis Using Gradient Based Polynomial Chaos In this section, the statistical characteristics for maximum response of the bladed disk obtained using polynomial chaos (PC) based surrogate model are presented. The values for mean and STD of normalized maximum response of bladed disk obtained from PC surrogate model are compared to Monte Carlo estimates based on 900 evaluations of the FE model of the bladed disk. For Monte Carlo simulations (MCS), the convergence of mean and STD of normalized maximum response for mode 1 and

Fig. 22: Mean and STD of normalized maximum blade response for 8EO excitation based on analysis of 150 different mistuning patterns for the case (a) 30 blades with random anisotropy angles (b) 37 blades with random anisotropy angles (c) all 75 blades having random anisotropy angles.

mode 2 due to 35EO excitation is shown in Fig. 26. It is clear from the figure that MCS requires more than 200 evaluations for the mean and STD to converge.

For a bladed disk with 225 random anisotropy angles, the number of terms in PC expansion of order 2 is 25651. Therefore, to reduce the computational cost involved in obtaining PC expansion for the stochastic response of the bladed disk, in addition to using gradient of the maximum response to evaluate the expansion coefficients, a cross-truncation scheme is used which significantly reduce the number of terms in the PC expansion by ignoring higher order interaction between parameters. For the present study the number of terms in the PC expansion was reduced from 25651 to 451 by using the truncation scheme. A comparison of the mean and STD of the normalized maximum response of the bladed disk obtained from PC expansion and MCS is provided in Tab. 2. While the Monte Carlo based statistics requires more than 200 evaluations to converge, the gradient PC based mean and STD has converged for 110 model evaluations. The accuracy of PC based mean value

Fig. 23: Mean and STD of normalized maximum blade response for 35EO excitation based on analysis of 150 different mistuning patterns for the case (a) 30 blades with random anisotropy angles (b) 37 blades with random anisotropy angles (c) all 75 blades having random anisotropy angles.

of normalized maximum response is satisfactory, but there is noticeable difference in the value of PC based STD compared to that obtained from Monte Carlo simulations. For linear bladed disk, the reduction in computational cost due to fewer FE model evaluations for gradient-PC based statistics is offset by the additional computational cost incurred due to the calculation of the gradients.

CONCLUSIONS

A method for calculating the sensitivity of the modal characteristics and forced response has been developed for high-fidelity FE models of material anisotropy mistuned bladed disks. An efficient approach using gradient based polynomial chaos has been developed to obtain statistics for forced response amplitudes considering the uncertainty in material anisotropy orientation of the blades.

The effect of anisotropy angle variation on the natural frequency values of tuned bladed disks has been analyzed

Fig. 24: Histogram for normalized maximum response of bladed disk for mode 1 due to (a) 8EO and (b) 35EO

Fig. 25: Histogram for normalized maximum response of bladed disk for mode 2 due to (a) 8EO and (b) 35EO

Fig. 26: Convergence of Monte Carlo estimates for normalized maximum response of bladed disk.

for natural frequencies of different families of modes and nodal diameters.

The effect of anisotropy mistuning on the forced response of the bladed disk has been analyzed for several different order excitations and frequency ranges. The studies have showed that the amplification factor can be higher than 2 for the excitation conditions and anisotropy mistuning patterns analyzed.

The method calculating the sensitivity of forced response has been validated and the sensitivities were studied in detail. The sensitivities of the disk dominated modes demonstrate a regular pattern. The sensitivity values for these modes are small, while the sensitivity values of the blade dominated and localized modes are significantly

TABLE 2: Statistics for normalized maximum response of a linear mistuned bladed disk to 35EO excitation

Mode family	FE model evaluations	Mean		Standard deviation	
		gradPCE	MCS	gradPCE	MCS
1	90	1.3589	1.4016	0.2387	0.1329
	110	1.4061	1.4016	0.2392	0.1329
	120	1.4001	1.4016	0.2482	0.1329
2	90	1.3388	1.3384	0.1924	0.1273
	110	1.3688	1.3384	0.1987	0.1273
	120	1.3625	1.3384	0.1990	0.1273

larger.

The statistical analysis of bladed disk assemblies mistuned by random anisotropy orientations has been performed. A comparison has been carried out for the mean and standard deviation values obtained by the developed method of gradient-based polynomial chaos expansion and the Monte Carlo simulations. It is shown that the developed method provides a convergence for the statistical characteristics using considerably less FE evaluations.

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